

JustREACH

D1.1- Project Handbook

WP1 – Project Management and coordination

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This report is mainly for use within the project, although it will be publicly available.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report provides an overview of the project management structure, internal communication, communication templates, and workflow process of the project JustREACH.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

Across Europe, local and regional authorities are under growing pressure to respond to the accelerating impacts of climate change while maintaining economic growth and social cohesion. Many face limited resources, complex policy requirements and the challenge of ensuring that adaptation measures are both effective and fair. The aim of JustREACH is to advance just climate resilience by enhancing the capacity of authorities, businesses and citizens to design and implement adaptation actions that align with regional innovation and development strategies. Through co-creation, knowledge integration and practical application, the project supports a more equitable and resilient transition for all regions. The JustREACH consortium consists of the following organisations.

TUD – DELFT UNIVESRITY OF TECHNOLOGY	NL	
BME – BUDAPEST UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMICS	HU	
THNK – THINK-E	BE	
JR – JOANNEUM RESEARCH	AT	
DAEM – DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS	GR	
QUB – QUEENS UNIVERSITY BELFAST	UK	
WIP – WIRTSCHAFT AND INFRASTUKTUR GMBH & CO. PLANUNGS KG	DE	
REGEA – NORTH-WEST CROATIA REGIONAL ENERGY AND CLIMATE AGENCY	HR	
LCF – BODENSEE-STIFTUNG	DE	
I-ENER – I-ENER	FR	
PBL – MINISTERIE VAN INFRASTUCUTUUR EN WATERSTAAT	NL	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	GR	
LUH – LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITEIT HANNOVER (L3S FORHUNGSZENTRUM)	DE	
UB – UNIVERSITY OF BERN	CH	

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1 Introduction

The aim of this handbook is to guide the project partners through the structures, strategies and processes leading to a successful project's implementation and monitoring. This handbook will be updated after each consortium meeting to provide the partners with a reference point during their journey within the JustREACH project.

This handbook does not include the information already available in the project's contractual documents mentioned in chapter 2 "Contractual Documents". This is done to avoid duplicating information. The aim of this document is to provide the partners with a practical tool that offers a quick overview of the project's progress, of their responsibilities and of the contractual documents that should be consulted to obtain detailed information on the project.

2 Contractual Documents

The contractual documents which govern and discipline the project are as follows:

- The Grant Agreement;
- The Consortium Agreement.

The **Grant Agreement** is an agreement between two parties, the one part is the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), and the other part is the Project Coordinator (PC).

The **Consortium Agreement** is a contractual document signed by all the JustREACH consortium partners. As reported in the Consortium Agreement: *"the purpose of this document is to specify with respect to the Project the relationship among the Parties, in particular concerning the organisation of the work between the Parties, the management of the Project and the Rights and obligations of the Parties concerning inter alia liability, Access Rights and dispute resolution."*

Both contractual documents are available in PDF format on the project repository, so that everyone can have access to it and consult it.

3 Project Purpose and Objectives

The development of adaptation plans by local and regional authorities has accelerated following the establishment of the European Climate Law (2021) and the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. At the same time, these authorities are also expected to develop regional innovation plans (following the so-called Smart Specialisation Strategy) to access financial support from the Cohesion Fund (for less developed regions) and the European Regional Development Fund. To implement the plans successfully and to avoid missed opportunities and negative consequences for those who are most vulnerable to changes, a systemic understanding of trade-offs and counteractions between these various policy objectives is needed. However, while local and regional authorities are expected to navigate the complex interlinkages of different targets set at the EU-level, they are also faced with urgent concerns locally, as well as challenged by a shortage of personnel and time, especially in regions with limited resources.

The objective of JustREACH is to enable local and regional authorities to overcome capacity limitations with: 1) easy-to-use, impact assessment tools that account for social justice, economic and environmental well-being (based on a framework designed to account for novel just resilience indicators, 2) a webtool which retrieves and integrates tailored information for their specific region across multiple existing knowledge hubs, 3) showing, not telling, how tools can be used in real-life decision-making settings through a transformative training program, and 4) helping local and regional authorities to explore new ways (i.e., with social learning videos) to mobilise their constituents – ensuring a just outcome for all.

JustREACH will co-design and test outputs with five pilot regions that are also consortium practice partners, all of whom are Mission Charter Signatories for climate adaptation. JustREACH partners also represent countries with regions receiving the Cohesion Fund (Greece, Croatia, Hungary) and the Just Transition Fund (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Germany, Greece, France, Ireland, the Netherlands). This allows the project to build on direct experience of past knowledge and concrete ongoing challenges to develop outputs that will be readily used. Representing all four EU climate adaptation regions—northern, western, central-eastern, and southern Europe—the pilot sites cover a diverse range of adaptation challenges taking place in urban, industrial, and rural settings. The project comprises an experienced interdisciplinary consortium of topic experts in their respective fields related to adaptation and regional development, including economics, sociology, urban studies, policy analysis and design, computational sciences, geography, simulation modeling, and critical sustainability studies.

Figure 1 The Conceptual Design of the JustREACH project

4 Management Structure

The management structure of the JustREACH project is designed to meet the following objectives:

- Efficient management and overall strategic project guidance and monitoring, including supervision of deliverables and milestones, the management of the risks and establishment of contingency plans, gender equity, and other non-technical aspects such as ethics processes.
- Building and maintaining effective communication channels within the consortium.
- Providing outputs for knowledge management and other related activities, such as Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and dissemination, solving problems as they may arise.
- Networking with other related projects, networks, and other initiatives.

The organisational structure of the project comprised the following bodies.

Project Coordination and Project Management team. The JustREACH coordinator is TU Delft, which is supported by WIP for the technical and financial management. The Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the European Commission. The Coordinator, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, performs the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. TU Delft has appointed two coordinators for JustREACH: BinBin Pearce and Amineh Ghorbani. WIP has appointed a technical and financial project manager for JustREACH: Silvia Caneva as Technical Project Manager, and Christine Mayer-Haege as Financial Project Manager. When needed, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation leads (Dimitra Spatharidou and Ioanna Bala) will also join to make sure that decisions about project management, which may affect the CDE strategy, will be communicated directly.

General Assembly (GA): the GA is constituted by the Coordinators, the Project Managers, and all the partners involved. **It is the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium**, which includes all project participants. The Coordinator chairs the GA. Every member of this committee owns a voting right. The GA is in charge of the overall direction and major decisions within the frame of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. All rules governing the GA, like meetings, voting rules and quorum, veto rights etc., are defined in the Consortium Agreement.

Work Package Leader (WPL): This position involves coordinating and ensuring suitable progress of the technical activities involved in a particular WP.

Each Work Package (WP) is led by a senior representative of an organisation with extensive expertise in all scientific-technical-social aspects of the respective WP.

Each WP Leader (WPL) is responsible for:

- the coordination and management of their WP, and
- for the quality of the content of expected deliverables and their timely delivery.

They will report to the GA and will assist the Coordinators and the Project Managers in the reporting duties to the European Commission (EC) within the limits of their competences. WPLs will be supported by several Task Leader (TLs), one for each task, who will take care of the work done at the

task level.

The appointed WP leaders by each organisation are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 Work Package leaders for JustREACH

WP #	WP name	WP Leader(s)
WP1	Project management and coordination	Coordinators (TU Delft): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BinBin Pearce and Amineh Ghorbani Project Managers (WIP): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Silvia Caneva (Technical) and Christine Mayer-Haegel (Finance)
WP2	Foundations of Just Resilience	Attila Buzázi (BME); Ioana Forgaci (TUD)
WP3	Behavioral enablers and drivers for climate adaptation and regional	Amineh Ghorbani and Annoek Reitsema (TUD)
WP4	Impact assessment towards just resilience	Olga Ivanova (PBL) and Theodoros Chatzivasileiadis (TUD)
WP5	Just Resilience Pilots	Michael Brenner-Fliesser (JR) and Sofia Delgado (THNK); BinBin Pearce (TUD)
WP6	Just resilience decision support tool for systemic decision-making	Avishek Anand and Mandeep Rathee (LUH)
WP7	Training, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication	Dimitra Spatharidou and Ioanna Bala (HOL)

Transdisciplinary Advisory Board (TAB): the TAB is created at the start of the project. Members of the TAB have been selected among the networks of the project partners. At the time of the preparation of the handbook, the potential TAB members that have been approached are:

- Dr. Markus Ehrman - Head of Research at the Environmental Energy Law Foundation (DE)
- Andrijana Krasnec - Leader of the Platform for sustainable finance in the Ministry of Finance (-HR)
- Thomas Dvorak, managing director of Fresh Thoughts (AT)
- Amy Bell - Director of Climate NI (UK)
- Karin Ingold - Professor at the Institute of Political Science at the University of Bern (CH)
- Maarten de Rijke – Professor of AI and information retrieval at the University of Amsterdam (NL)
- Oliver Zieger - Coordinator of the Ticca4danu project

In case they are not available, we will contact the following people to make up a minimum of 5

members of the TAB:

- Per Becker - Prof. at Lund University in Sweden (SW)
- Johanna Höffken – Associate Professor at TU Eindhoven (NL)
- Markus Hadler – Professor at the University of Graz (AT)

TAB members are scientific and policy experts recognised in academic disciplines related to climate adaptation and regional policy, representatives of citizen engagement organisations and representatives of organisations who are working with citizens on the ground for implementing climate adaptation initiatives.

The role of a TAB member is to provide expertise and feedback of the project's progress and key outputs. TAB members:

- Can be asked to meet in person and/or online during the project to attend General Assembly meetings and/or Management Board meetings.
- May be approached (with their permission) by the Project Management or various partners of the consortium for specific ad-hoc, one-on-one meetings for advice
- May be requested to perform a review of a portion of a specific project output (e.g., recruiting guidelines, modelling input, advanced draft of deliverables)

TAB members will have both fixed and optional responsibilities. Members will be asked which optional responsibilities they will be open to meeting and will agree to fulfilling all fixed responsibilities.

Fixed responsibilities are:

- Attending 1 meeting (1 hour) per month (see section 1.3) that are requested by JustREACH project partners.
- Once a year, keep the project management team/relevant consortium partners apprised of new developments in their own field or work that may have an impact or may be of interest to the JustREACH project either through a meeting or by email.

Optional responsibilities are:

- Provide feedback of project outputs where the TAB member has expertise or interest.
- Raise awareness and/or help expand the impact of JustREACH and its outputs amongst the TAB member's network.
- Attendance of General Assembly Meetings where specific input is needed.

The fixed time commitment of the TAB member will be, on average, 1 hour per month during the duration of the JustREACH project.

Any additional time commitment will be taken on voluntarily by TAB members and will not be expected.

5 Work Breakdown Structure

Usually, the Participant Portal is used by the Coordinator, the Project Manager and the Leader of the Communication and Dissemination Work Package.

Therefore, it is fundamental to provide the project partners with a tool they can use to obtain an overview of the submitted deliverables and achieved milestones. The Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) is the tool adopted by the JustREACH Consortium and gives a detailed view into the project, and shows what work the project encompasses. It helps to easily communicate the work and processes involved in executing the project. The Coordinator and the partners use the WBS to be informed about the responsible partner for the completion of each task, the timing for the execution and the outcomes including deliverables and milestones.

The overview of the deliverables and milestones already submitted and achieved until the submission of this report are highlighted in Table 2.

Table 2. Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

WP	Task #	Task name	Leader	Start	End	Outcome (Partner, Deadline)
WP1	Project management and coordination		WIP	M1	M48	
	T1.1	Administer the contract with the European Commission and oversee financial and legal issues	WIP	M1	M48	MS1: minutes kick-off meeting (WIP, 14 Oct 2025): achieved
	T1.2	Management and coordination of administrative progress, meetings and establishment of the Transdisciplinary Advisory Board (TAB)	WIP and TUD	M1	M48	D1.1: Project handbook/website (TUD, 14 Dec 2025)
	T1.3	Scientific coordination within the project and synergies with other relevant EU projects	TUD	M1	M48	D1.3: Synergies with EU projects (TUD, 14 Mar 2027) D1.6: Synergies with EU projects update (TUD, 14 Sep 2028) D1.7: Synergies with EU final update (TUD, 14 Sep 2029)
	T1.4	Data management plan and ethics requirements	WIP and TUD	M1	M48	D1.2: Data management plan (TUD, 14 Mar 2026) D1.8: Data management plan first update (TUD, 14 Mar 2027) D1.4: Data management plan update (TUD, 14 Sep 2028) D1.5: Data management plan final update (TUD, 14 Sep 2029)
WP2	Foundations of Just Resilience					
	T2.1	Review and consolidate EU knowledge and data on climate adaptation and smart specialisation.	BME	M1	M7	D2.1: Status quo report on status of EU knowledge on climate adaptation and smart specialisation (BME, 14 Apr 2026)
	T2.2	Conduct a systematic scientific	BME	6	18	D2.2: Synthesis of existing assessment frameworks

	literature review on the assessment approaches to climate justice, climate resilience, and maladaptation				on climate justice, climate resilience and maladaptation (BME, 10 Mar 2027)
T2.3	Develop framework and indicators for just climate resilience	BME	6	18	M2.1 Iterative feedback sessions with policy makers, academic experts and civil society organisations (BME, 30 Sep 2026)
T2.4	Validating the IJR framework	BME	19	42	D2.3: Just Resilience Checklist (BME, 12 Oct 2027) D2.4: Final IJF Framework (BME, 12 Mar 2029)
WP3	Behavioral enablers and drivers for climate adaptation and regional				
T3.1	Conducting Surveys	TUD	1	14	D3.1: Survey analysis (TUD, 11 Nov 2026) M3.1: 300 surveys completed per pilot site (TUD, 31 July 2026)
T3.2	Developing an agent-based model of household adoption of climate adaptation measures	TUD	7	18	D3.2: An abstract ABM of climate adaptation behavior (TUD, 10 Mar 2027)
T3.3	Development of simulation models for studying spillover effects and maladaptation pathways	TUD	19	26	D3.3: ABM of multi-region climate adaptation (TUD, 10 Nov 2027)
T3.4	Validating just resilience indicators	TUD	24	36	D3.4: Indicators to measure justice in climate adaptation (TUD, 11 Sept 2028)
WP4	Impact assessment towards just resilience				
T4.1	Developing adaptation pathway scenarios	PBL	12	20	D4.1: Policy briefs on Adaptation Pathways (PBL, 12 May 2027)

	T4.2	Integrating behavioral enablers and drivers to the impact assessment model	PBL	21	30	M4.1: Integration of CGE and ABM models completed (PBL, 31 Oct 2027)
	T4.3	Incorporating Biodiversity	PBL	21	30	D4.2: Technical documentation and demonstrator of the integrated model (PBL, 10 Mar 2028)
	T4.4	Building the impact assessment database	PBL	31	41	D4.3: Assessment database (PBL, 12 Sep 2028)
WP5	Just Resilience Pilots					
	T5.1	Preparation of pilot sites and co-producing knowledge of implementation gaps	THNK	1	12	M1 (a-e): Just Resilience Mission workshops (THNK, 30 Mar 2026) D5.1: Systematic Representation of Barriers and Opportunities (THNK, 10 Sep 2026)
	T5.2	Co-producing needs, values and indicators for just resilience of stakeholder groups	JR	13	18	D5.2: Needs, Values, and Indicators Report (JR, 10 Mar 2027)
	T5.3	Co-designing and co-creating implementation pathways	JR	19	40	D5.3: Interlinking Systems Map (JR, 10 Sep 2027) D5.4: Just Resilience Mission Pathways (JR, 10 Jan 2029) D5.5: Enriched Implementation Guidelines (JR, 10 Jan 2029)
	T5.4	Social Learning Videos for overcoming implementation gaps	UB	1	42	D5.6: Social Learning Videos (UB, 12 Sep 2028) D5.7: Social Media Analysis of SLV Impact (UB, 9 Jan 2029)
	T5.5	Testing JustREACH Prism with pilot sites	JR	25	40	M5.4: Prism tested in pilot sites (JR, Jan 2029)
WP6	Just resilience decision support tool for systemic decision-making					
	T6.1	Characterising the users of the decision-support tool based on activities on existing platforms	LUH	6	12	M6.1: User group characterization (LUH, Sep 2026) D6.5: User group characterization (LUH, 14 Mar 2027)

T6.2	Building a query understanding module that can decipher underlying user intent	LUH	12	36	D6.1: Query comprehension module (LUH, 12 Sep 2028) D6.6: Prism user interface (LUH, 14 Sep 2028)
T6.3	Building the retrieval and document comprehension module	LUH	18	36	D6.2: Retrieval and document comprehension module (LUH, 14 Sep 2028)
T6.4	Building the user interface for tool	LUH	24	36	M6.2: User interface ready (LUH, 30 Sep 2028)
T6.5	Compiling, Testing and Validating the JustREACH Prism	LUH	24	46	D6.3: The JustREACH Prism and User Manual (LUH, 14 May 2029) D6.4: Qualitative analysis of JustREACH Prism (14 Jul 2029)
WP7 Training, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication					
T7.1	Identifying target audiences	HOL	1	6	D7.1: Identifying target audiences (HOL, 14 Dec 2025)
T7.2	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan	HOL	2	4	D7.2: CDE plan (HOL, 14 Feb 2026)
T7.3	Developing and delivering communication and dissemination activities	HOL	2	48	M7.1: Creation of project website (HOL, 31 Dec 2025)
T7.4	JustREACH Transformation Bootcamp	UB	30	48	M7.2: Call for applicants for JustREACH Transformation Bootcamp launched (HOL, 30 Mar 2029) M7.3: JustREACH Transformation Bootcamp concluded (UB, 30 July 2029) M7.4:

					Online course material uploaded to Coursera/Open edX (UB, 15 Sep 2029)
T7.5	Final event	HOL/TUD	43	48	M7.5: Final event (HOL/TUD, 15 Sep 2029)
T7.6	Open science and data management	TUD	1	48	See D1.2

6 Quality Assurance

Quality Assurance is the process adopted to ensure that the project tasks are properly implemented, and the deliverables generated with the required high-quality level. The quality assurance of the project was obtained by monitoring and assessing the progress and results provided by the different work packages in a continuous way by setting up a series of activities at the beginning of the project to help achieve the requested quality during the project's execution. These activities lead to producing high-quality deliverables and proper and complete task implementation.

6.1 Project Templates

The first step to guarantee the quality of the project outcomes is defined by the development of project templates in line with the project identity. The templates of JustREACH are available on the TU Delft Teams folder at the link:

[JustREACH templates](#)

They have been prepared at the beginning of the project by the partner HOL. They are the template for the poster, deliverables and powerpoint presentation (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Poster Design

JustREACH

Dx.x- DELIVERABLE TITLE

Wx.x-WP Title

DD/MM/YYYY

Figure 3 Word Template

Figure 4 Template Power Point Presentation

6.2 Deliverables Peer Review Process

Deliverables are the most important tools which report the work implemented and the results of the project. Most of the deliverables of JustREACH are public and accessible to a wide range of stakeholders. Therefore, their quality is of utmost importance. All deliverables generated by the respective leaders will pass through an internal quality review process to ensure a high quality from different aspects such as structure, content, objectives, and alignment with the GA. Unless this process is executed successfully, the deliverable will not be submitted to the EC.

The quality review process included the following steps:

1. The task leader develops the deliverable using the deliverable template which was developed by HOL at the beginning of the project to ensure a unified identity for all project deliverables. When the first draft is elaborated, the task leader sends it to the assigned reviewer **at least 3 weeks before the deadline**.
2. **The reviewer has 1 week to assess the deliverable**. The reviewer sends the revised deliverable to the task leader **2 weeks before the deadline**. After receiving the comments from the reviewer, the task leader prepares an updated version and sends it to the reviewer for final approval **at least 1 week before the deadline**.
3. Once approved by the reviewer, the task leader sends the deliverable to the Coordinator **at least 3 working days before the deadline**.
4. The Coordinator submits the final version to the EC via the Participant Portal.

The Project Manager has provided a **Quality Evaluation Form (QEF)** to assist the reviewers in their assessment process (Figure 3).

Revision of DX.Y	
Reviewer name	
Organisation name	
Evaluation date	

Criteria	Questions	Y	N
Consistency	Are the title, number, type, and dissemination level of the Deliverable in line with the definition in the GA?		
	Is the objective and purpose of the Deliverable easily recognisable and identifiable?		
	Is the Deliverable consistent with the associated task description in the Grant Agreement?		
	Are interpretations/conclusions sound, justified by the data, and consistent with the objectives?		
	Is the document length appropriate (less than 100 pages)?		
Content	Is the content relevant and consistent with the purpose of the Deliverable?		
	Is any off-topic content present?		
	Is the reported information extensive, correct, and precise?		
	Is the quantity of data/information adequate?		
Structure	Is the Deliverable drafted according to the official template?		
	Does the Deliverable follow a coherent organisation: EC Summary Requirements, Preface, Executive Summary, Contents, Bibliography?		
	Are figures and tables correctly referred to in the text?		
	Are the figures of high quality?		
	Are the tables complete and readable?		
	Do figures and tables include dedicated captions?		
	Do hyperlinks and references work?		
Vocabulary and style	Is there a list of used abbreviations?		
	Are lexical choices and styles appropriate?		
Spelling and morphosyntactic correctness	Is the Deliverable written in high-quality English?		
	Is punctuation correct?		
	Is the text fluent, readable, and clear?		

Figure 5 Quality Evaluation Form (QEF)

The Project Manager has also provided the excel file **Deliverables Peer Review Process for Project JustREACH** to identify the reviewers and keep track of the revision process (Figure 4).

Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Type	Dissemination	Lead Beneficiary	Reviewer	Actual Delivery Date	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	D1	Project handbook/website	R	PU	TUD	HOL		14 Dec 2025
WP1	D1.2	D2	Data management plan	DMP	PU	TUD	JR		14 Mar 2026
WP1	D1.3	D28	Synergies with EU projects	R	PU	TUD			14 Mar 2027
WP1	D1.4	D29	Data management plan update	DMP	PU	TUD	JR		14 Sep 2028
WP1	D1.5	D30	Data management plan final update	DMP	PU	TUD	JR		14 Sep 2029
WP1	D1.6	D31	Synergies with EU projects update	R	PU	TUD			14 Sep 2028
WP1	D1.7	D32	Synergies with EU final update	R	PU	TUD			14 Sep 2029
WP1	D1.8	D33	Data management plan first update	DMP	PU	TUD	JR		14 Mar 2027
WP2	D2.1	D3	Status quo report on EU knowledge	R	SEN	BME			14 Apr 2026
WP2	D2.2	D4	Synthesis of existing assessment fr	R	PU	BME			14 Mar 2027
WP2	D2.3	D5	Just Resilience Checklist	R	PU	BME			14 Oct 2027
WP2	D2.4	D6	Final IJR framework	R	PU	BME			14 Mar 2029
WP3	D3.1	D7	Survey analysis	R	PU	TUD			14 Nov 2026
WP3	D3.2	D8	An abstract ABM of climate adaptati	OTHER	PU	TUD			14 Mar 2027
WP3	D3.3	D9	ABM of multi-region climate adaptati	OTHER	PU	TUD			14 Nov 2027
WP3	D3.4	D10	Indicators to measure justice in clima	R	PU	TUD			14 Sep 2028
WP4	D4.1	D11	Policy briefs on Adaptation Pathway	R	PU	PBL			14 May 2027
WP4	D4.2	D12	Technical documentation and demon	OTHER	PU	PBL			14 Mar 2028
WP4	D4.3	D13	Assessment database	DATA	PU	PBL			14 Sep 2028
WP5	D5.1	D14	Systematic Representation of Barrie	R	PU	THNK			14 Sep 2026
WP5	D5.2	D15	Needs, Values, and Indicators Repo	R	PU	JR			14 Mar 2027
WP5	D5.3	D16	Interlinking Systems Map	R	PU	JR			14 Sep 2027
WP5	D5.4	D17	Just Resilience Mission Pathways	R	PU	JR			14 Jan 2029
WP5	D5.5	D18	Enriched Implementation Guidelines	R	PU	JR			14 Jan 2029
WP5	D5.6	D19	Social Learning Videos	DEC	PU	UB			14 Sep 2028
WP5	D5.7	D20	Social Media Analysis of SLV Impact	R	PU	UB			14 Jan 2029
WP6	D6.1	D21	Query comprehension module	OTHER	PU	LUH			14 Sep 2028
WP6	D6.2	D22	Retrieval and document comprehens	OTHER	PU	LUH			14 Sep 2028
WP6	D6.3	D23	The JustREACH Prism and User Mar	OTHER	PU	TUD			14 May 2029
WP6	D6.4	D24	Qualitative analysis of JustREACH P	R	PU	TUD			14 Jul 2029
WP6	D6.5	D37	User group characterization	R	PU	LUH			14 Mar 2027
WP6	D6.6	D38	Prism user interfact	DEM	PU	LUH			14 Sep 2028
WP7	D7.1	D25	Identifying target audiences	R	PU	HOL			14 Dec 2025
WP7	D7.2	D26	CDE plan	R	PU	HOL	WIP		14 Feb 2026
WP7	D7.3	D27	Transformation Bootcamp Playbook	R	PU	UB			14 Aug 2029
WP7	D7.4	D34	CDE update 1	R	PU	HOL	WIP		14 Mar 2027
WP7	D7.5	D35	CDE update 2	R	PU	HOL	WIP		14 Sep 2028
WP7	D7.6	D36	CDE update 3	R	PU	HOL	WIP		14 Sep 2029

Figure 6 Deliverable peer review process

7 Internal Communication Management

The success of a project relies on the efficient and timely internal communication among the project partners on technical, administrative and financial issues. The internal communication strategy aims at keeping all the partners fully informed about the project status, the planning and all other issues which are important to the partners in order to obtain maximum transparency for all involved partners and to increase the synergy of the cooperation.

The internal communication strategy of the JustREACH project uses the following channels: project meetings (in person and online), direct contact (e-mail, telephone), and file sharing (repositories).

7.1 Project meetings

Project meetings are the optimal channel for keeping constant and efficient communication between the consortium partners. On these occasions, the partners are informed about what has happened in the previous project period, the problems faced and the results of their work and are reminded about their tasks for the next period. Also, project meetings are the best occasion during which clarifications, misunderstandings and common brainstorming through personal communication take place.

The project meetings of the GA are held every six months, alternating between in-person and online, with hybrid access available for those unable to attend the in-person meetings.

The kick-off meeting was held in Delft at TU Delft on 15th and 16th September 2025. The 1st GA will be held online in the middle of March 2026. Proposed dates for each GA will be discussed in project meetings and decided over online scheduling polls organised by the Coordinator, at an early stage, i.e., at least a few months before a physical/hybrid meeting.

As project meetings take place every 6 months, monthly online meetings are scheduled between TU Delft and WIP (Project Management Meeting) and with all partners (Project Meeting).

WPs Leaders and Tasks Leaders Missing information/ are required to attend monthly....

7.2 Internal communication

E-mails, online calls, as well as short messaging via the Basecamp platform are the most common ways for direct exchange of information between consortium partners. They permit quick and urgent discussions, brainstorming, exchange of information and provision of updates on project status and progress.

In order to facilitate this direct communication among the project partners, a project contact database was created by WIP at the beginning of the project. It includes the list of the main project contact persons responsible for operational matters (i.e. implementation of the project activities) and the administrative contact persons responsible for administrative and financial issues, along with their contact details (name, work telephone number and email).

The list was uploaded on the project repository at the beginning of the project and it will be constantly updated by WIP.

7.3 Project Repositories

JustREACH makes use of two repositories:

- Microsoft Teams (Figure 5)
- Basecamp (Figure 6)

The contact details list and other sensitive information are stored in TU Delft-based Microsoft Teams to be in line with the GDPR. An overview of the files organised on Teams and of the structure of Basecamp is provided in the screenshots below. Files which require the input of, or which contain information that needs to be accessed by a member of the consortium outside of one's own institution, are kept. Sensitive information with personal information that are necessary for conducting research and maintaining contacts will be kept in secure databases at the partner responsible for the output to minimise the sharing of sensitive information. More details about how data is managed will be provided in deliverable D.1.2 Data Management, due in March 2026.

The JustREACH group on Teams and Basecamp are both managed by TU Delft. While Teams is used as a repository for data and documents, Basecamp is a tool that provides partners with a continuous progress monitoring through a "To-Do-List", reminders of deliverables, and milestone deadlines. No files are stored there.

The data is organised by work package and by topics that are relevant to every work package.

Figure 7 Teams folder organisation

Home Lineup Pings Hey! Activity My Stuff Find

JustREACH

No updates yet

Set up people AR AA C DS IB RL S + 22 just following

Message Board

- Pre-financing distribution info available**
FYI — here. JustREACH_budget_prefinancing...
- Teams group restructured**
Announcement — Please check the new...
- If you have a question about financial questions regarding JustREACH.....**
- Consortium Agreement**
FYI — Dear all, Thanks for your patience as w...
- Last call for nominations of the advisory board**
Announcement — Dear all, Thanks for those...

To-dos

Project update meeting 29 Oct 2025

- Double check financial information from partners
Oct 31 BinBin
- Send repeating invites to all meetings
Oct 30 Silvia
- Send distribution of funds to Loes after receiving from Christine
Nov 3 BinBin
- Complete deliverables and internal review spreadsheet
Nov 18 Silvia

Chat

Chat casually with your team, ask questions, and share news without ceremony.

Start chatting

Schedule

WED, OCT 29

- (Communicate this after getting NDA from Silvia)
Invite members of ABoard that you nominated

Figure 8 Basecamp home page

8 Project Website

The project website will be fully launched by 31 December 2025, as indicated in the work structure (Table 2). Below are screenshots of the website’s home page. The website is intended for the general public, as well as for related Mission adaptation projects and community of practice members to follow the progress of our project. It will serve as the main platform for sharing the latest news, events, and project outputs.

Figure 9 Website screenshot